

AWT Weekly Survey

Start of Block: Controle

Q16 Welcome to this week's survey!

Ex Please answer the following questions about your previous workweek.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Last week, I felt mentally exhausted from my work.	<input type="radio"/>				
Last week, I found it hard to recover my energy after a day at work.	<input type="radio"/>				
Last week, I felt physically exhausted.	<input type="radio"/>				

En Please answer the following questions.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Last week, I felt bursting with energy at work.	<input type="radio"/>				
Last week, I was enthusiastic about my job.	<input type="radio"/>				
Last week, I was immersed in my work.	<input type="radio"/>				

Open Is there anything else you want to share about last week? (optional)

End of Block: Controle
